

Physicochemical Parameters of Obibia Stream, Amawbia Awka South Local Government Area Anambra State, Nigeria

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Suggested Citation

Eze, H.C., Obasi C.J., Ikegwuonu, E.A., Enweluzor, A.C., Chukwujekwu, A.G., & Okonkwo, N.N. (2024). Physicochemical Parameters of Obibia Stream, Amawbia Awka South Local Government Area Anambra State, Nigeria. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 2(3), 173-184.
DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2024.2\(3\).15](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2024.2(3).15)

Abstract:

Nigeria has sufficient shallow and deep water, that if polluted can be unhealthy to human life. Obibia stream is an essential water source in Amawbia-Nibo axis of Awka, Anambra State, Nigeria especially for its drinking purposes, urban agricultural usage and domestic uses. Water quality is often altered by anthropogenic activities, leachates and run off. It is therefore necessary to determine the influence of seasonal changes and its effects on the health of populace in this locality. The aim of this study is to evaluate the influence of seasonal changes on the physicochemical parameters of Obibia stream. The statistical analysis was done using ANOVA, Post Hoc Test, Correlation analyses and Paired Test. The physicochemical parameters were within the WHO standard, and the values obtained

in the wet season were non-significantly ($p > 0.05$) higher than the values obtained from the dry season, although there was moderate correlation between some selected parameters. The physicochemical parameters were observed to be higher in the wet season than the dry season. Therefore, adequate treatment before use and periodic evaluation of its physicochemical qualities are recommended.

Keywords: *water resources, anthropogenic activity, seasonal changes, pollution.*

Introduction

Water is the basis of life and primary need for all vital processes. With increasing industrialization and population growth, water sources available

for various purposes such as drinking, recreation, agriculture and aquaculture have been adulterated with industrial as well as animal and domestic wastes.

Lakes, streams and rivers have important multi-usage components such as sources of drinking water, irrigation, fishery and energy production. Water is a scarce and fading resource, and its management can have an impact on the flow and the biological quality of streams and streams (Esharegoma *et al.*, 2018). Water meant for drinking should be free from harmful chemicals, suspended materials, undesirable taste, color and odor. Drinking water from natural sources is usually polluted as a result of man's activities, thus rendering supplies harmful to the body. This pollution results from eutrophication, introduction of sewage and also toxic wastes from industries into the water body. According to American Public Health Association (2012), about 1.2 billion people globally lack safe drinking water, and 50% of the populace in developing countries still have no reasonable access to safe and sustained water supplies.

In Awka, the Anambra State capital, access to adequate urban water supply from the State's water corporation is a serious problem facing the inhabitants since 1999. Hence, to meet their demand for potable water supply, the inhabitants of this State have survived by constructing water supply systems, reservoirs, wells and boreholes. Others patronize water vendors; rain water collected from roofs and streams. Proliferation in the use of water from alternative sources, like shallow hand dug wells and boreholes, water from streams and streams, leads to the utilization of water with questionable qualities for domestic activities. Again, solid wastes are generated at a rate faster than they are disposed of by the designated authorities.

Polluted water is the major reason for the spread of many endemic diseases like skin and eye infections, cholera, tuberculosis, typhoid, diarrhea, viral hepatitis A and even death. Mortality in children less than five years due to water related diseases annually is estimated to be about 4 million in under developed countries and World Health Organization also estimated that 3.4 million people, mostly children, die every year from water-related disease (Esharegoma *et al.* 2018).

Water quality is defined in terms of the chemical, physical, and biological characteristics of water, usually in respect to its suitability for an intended purpose. Worldwide, indicator organisms such as the coliform bacterium, *Escherichia coli* and faecal streptococci have been used to assess faecal pollution and deterioration in fresh water sources such as lakes, streams, underground waters and streams (Esharegoma *et al.*, 2018). The microbiological and physicochemical parameters of different fresh water systems (stream, stream, ocean etc.) have been studied by various researchers such as Esharegoma *et al.* (2018). Faecal contamination of streams is a major water quality issue in many fast growing cities where population growth far exceeds the rate of development of wastewater collection and treatment. Solid wastes are indiscriminately dumped at available empty land, on the streets and in gutters. Also, automobile repair shops scattered all over the town generate repulsive and objectionable view sights, which reduce the aesthetic value of the environment. Indiscriminate disposal of used motor oil (condemned oil) and grease in the environment may result in the contamination of water resources and death of aquatic biota. The fertilizers and pesticides used by the farmers to improve crop yield are eventually leached into the streams and streams where they may contaminate water and facilitate eutrophication (Ikuo, 2014). Industrial effluents and other wastes not properly recycled or treated are discharged into the environment due to inadequate environmental impact monitoring or enforcement in the State. Wastes generated from above-named activities in one way or the other find a way into the hydrological cycle thereby polluting or contaminating water resources (Obiefuna and Sheriff, 2011). This is so because most of the water is not protected or monitored qualitatively, thereby exposing them to varying types of pollutants — both chemical and microbial pollutants. Therefore, water from these sources is used ignorantly despite the cumulative health implication of such exercise.

Polluted water is the major reason for the spread of many endemic diseases like skin and eye infections, cholera, tuberculosis, typhoid,

diarrhea, viral hepatitis A and even death. Mortality in children less than five years due to water related diseases annually is estimated to be about 4 million in under developed countries and World Health Organization also estimated that 3.4 million people, mostly children, die every year from water-related disease (Esharegoma *et al.* 2018). This study investigated the influence of seasonal changes on the physiochemical parameters of Obibia stream, Awka, Anambra State, Nigeria.

Materials and Methods

Study Area

Stream Obibia is a stream (class H - Hydrographic) in Nigeria (Africa) with the region font code of Africa/Middle East (Awka). Its coordinates are 6°13'60" N and 7°9'0" E in DMS (Degrees Minutes Seconds) or 6.23333 and 7.15 (in decimal degrees). Stream Obibia is situated and surrounded by tributaries from parts of Nibo, Amawbia, Umuawulu and Awka towns in Awka South Local Government of Anambra State. The Obibia Stream is the source of water supply for domestic and agricultural purposes in the eastern parts of the town.

Sample Collection as Described by APHA (2012)

A total of 30 freshwater samples from different sampling sources or sites along Obibia Stream were collected from May, 2015 to July, 2015 which represent the rainy season and December, 2015 to February, 2016 which represent the dry season. Samples were taken from five different sites in duplicates. The first source (site one) was where washing of bitter leaf, cassava steeping and processing of other foods were done. Source two was the site for bathing and swimming, source three was situated where runoff from car wash and block industry entered the water, source four was where drinking water was collected and source five was where run off from steep-sloped agricultural land entered the water.

On each occasion, two 500 ml water samples were collected in 1 L sterile containers from each

site. The containers were initially washed with detergent and thereafter rinsed with sterile distilled water. The containers were also rinsed with the water samples at the point of collection before being transferred immediately into cooler containing ice packs and transported to Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu Microbiology laboratory for processing within 24 h of collection. These water samples were collected for physicochemical analyses as thus:

Physicochemical Analyses of the Water Samples in Different Seasons

Determination of temperature

The temperature was determined using a centigrade thermometer. The thermometer was immersed into a beaker containing the samples and the temperature value was recorded when

the reading stabilized as done by Eze *et al.* (2013).

Determination of pH

The pH of the water samples was determined using a pH meter. The pH meter was first standardized using a phosphate buffer to pH value of 7.0. After that, the electrode was dipped into the water sample contained in a beaker and the pH value was taken. This was done in triplicate as described by Eze *et al.* (2013).

Determination of colour

Measurement of colour was by visual comparator. This was done by comparing the sample with standard colour solution. The standard colour solution was prepared using 1.2 g potassium chloroplatinate (K_2PtCl_6) and 1.0 g cobalt chloride ($CoCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$). The test samples and the prepared standard were dispensed into sterile test tubes. The tubes were placed on a white surface to be able to match the colours. The colour of the test sample closed to the standard was chosen and the matching unit recorded as described Agboli *et al.* (2017).

Determination of odour and taste

Odour and taste were investigated by simply using human nose (olfactory nerve) and tongue as receptors. The sample was tasted and taste was recorded. An odourless bottle with stopper was used. The bottle was vigorously shaken for

3 seconds to determine any odour. The odour was interpreted as objectionable or unobjectionable as described by Agboli *et al.* (2017).

Determination of biochemical oxygen demand (BOD₅)

The biochemical oxygen demand (BOD₅) of the water samples were determined using Wrinkler's method as described by APHA (2012). The sample was carefully collected in a 300 ml BOD bottle, avoiding any kinds of bubbling and trapping of air bubbles in the bottle after placing the stopper. To the 50 ml sample taken in the conical flask 2 ml of manganese sulphate (MnSO₄) and 2 ml of sodium azide solution were added well below the surface from the wall of the bottle. A precipitate appeared, the stopper was placed tightly and the bottle was shaken by inverting the bottle repeatedly to ensure proper mixing of the contents. The bottle was kept for some time to settle. Thereafter, 2 ml of conc. H₂SO₄ was added to it and shaken well to dissolve all the precipitate. Then 50 ml of sample was taken in a conical flask and titrated against sodium thiosulphate (Na₂S₂O₃) of 0.025 N using starch as an indicator. At the end point the initial blue color changed to colorless.

Calculation:

$$DO \left(\frac{\text{mg}}{\text{L}} \right) = \frac{(\text{ml} \times N) \text{ of titrant} \times 8 \times 1000}{\frac{V_2 \times (V_1 - V)}{V_1}} \quad (1)$$

Where V₁ = volume of sample bottle after placing the stopper

V₂ = volume of part of content titrated

V = volume of MnSO₄ and KI added

The general equation for the determination of a BOD₅ value is given below:

$$BOD_5 \left(\frac{\text{mg}}{\text{l}} \right) = \frac{D_1 - D_5}{0.05} \quad (2)$$

Where D₁ = initial dissolved oxygen (DO) of the sample, D₅ = final dissolved oxygen (DO)

of the sample after 5 days, and P = decimal volumetric fraction of sample used (0.05).

Total dissolved solids (TDS) determination

The total dissolved solids of the water samples were determined according to the method of APHA (2012). Firstly, the fiber filter discs were prepared by placing it, wrinkled side up, in the filtration apparatus. Vacuum was applied and the disc washed with three successive 20 ml washings of distilled water. Continuous suction were then applied to remove all traces of water. Clean evaporating dishes were heated to 180 ± 2 °C in oven (DHG- 9053AA, Life Assurance Scientific, UK) for 1 h, cooled and stored in a desiccator until needed. They were weighed immediately before use. Then 50 ml of well mixed samples were filtered through the glass-fibre filters; washed with three successive 10 ml volumes of distilled water, allowing complete draining between washings. Suctions were continually applied for about 3 minutes after filtration was completed. The filtrates were transferred to a weighed evaporating dishes and evaporated to dryness on a steam bath (Techmel M3021, India). The evaporating dishes were finally dried for 1 h in oven at 180 ± 2 °C, cooled in a desiccator to balance temperature and weighed. Total dissolved solid values were determined using the equation given below:

$$TDS = \frac{(A - B) \times 10^3 \text{ mg/l}}{\text{Sample volume in ml}} \quad (3)$$

Where A = weight of dish + solids (mg)

B = weight of dish before use (mg)

Total suspended solids (TSS) determination

The method of APHA (2012) was used. The total suspended solids were determined by subtracting the result of total dissolved solids from total solid as follows:

$$\text{Total solids (TS)} - \text{Total dissolved solids (TDS)} = \text{Total Suspended solids (TSS)} \quad (4)$$

Total solids (TS) determination

The method of APHA (2012) was used. One hundred milliliter of the water samples were measured into a pre-weighed dishes and evaporated to dryness at 103°C on a steam bath. The evaporated samples were dried in an oven (DHG- 9053AA, Life Assurance Scientific, UK) for 1 h at 103 - 105°C, cooled in a desiccator and their constant weights were recorded. Total solids were calculated as follows:

$$\text{Total solids} = \text{Total Suspended Solids} + \text{Total Dissolved Solids} \quad (5)$$

Determination of water conductivity

Electrical conductivity measurement was done using a digital conductivity meter (DSS – 11A, China) by adopting the method described by AOAC (2012). Standardization of the meter was performed using 0.1 N KCl at 25 °C. After that, the electrode was dipped into the water sample

and the reading was taken. This was done in triplicate and the mean value was calculated as described by Eze *et al.* (2013).

Results

Physicochemical Properties of the Water Samples in Different Seasons

Physicochemical properties in wet season

The result of the physicochemical characteristics of the five samples collected in the month of May, 2015 of wet season were presented in Table1. From the result, Sample 4, 2, 3 and 1 had the highest values of temperature, pH, BOD, TSS, TDS, TS and conductivity. Most samples were muddy, unobjectionable and not determined in colour, odour and taste. Statistically, there were significant differences ($P < 0.05$) in the mean of the samples indicating that all the physicochemical parameters do not have the same influence on the samples.

Table1. Physicochemical Characteristics of the Five Samples Collected in the Month of May, 2015 of Wet Season

Parameter	Source 1	Source 2	Source 3	Source 4	Source 5	Who Standard
Temperature	29.250±0.04	27.820±0.03	29.200±0.01	29.500±0.00	29.430±0.1	25-40
Ph	6.920±0.05	7.890±0.01	7.580±0.00	6.990±0.01	7.210±0.03	6.5-8.5
Colour	Muddy	Muddy	Slightly Muddy	Slightly Muddy	Muddy	Na
Odour	Un-Objectionable	Un-Objectionable	Un-Objectionable	Un-Objectionable	Un-Objectionable	Na
BOD	258.000±0.03	278.200±0.01	286.000±0.03	240.000±0.00	260.000±0.02	20-40
TSS	0.060±0.01	0.058±0.00	0.048±0.01	0.045±0.01	0.045±0.02	Na
TDS	70.800±0.03	70.000±0.01	69.440±0.02	70.300±0.00	70.200±0.01	500
TS	70.860±0.00	70.060±0.02	69.480±0.00	70.340±0.01	70.250±0.00	500
Conductivity	1.430±0.01	1.240±0.01	2.500±0.00	2.100±0.01	1.500±0.02	500

Note: BOD = Biochemical oxygen demand; TSS = Total suspended solid; TDS = Total dissolved solid; TS = Total solid, NA = Not available

The result of the physicochemical characteristics of the five samples collected in the month of June, 2015 of wet season were presented in Table 2. From the result, Sample 2, 1, and 3 had the highest values of temperature, conductivity, pH, TSS, TDS, TS and BOD. Most samples

were muddy, objectionable and not determined in colour, odour and taste. Statistically, there were significant differences ($P < 0.05$) in the mean of the samples indicating that the physicochemical parameters do not have the same influence on the samples.

Table 2. Physicochemical Characteristics of the Five Samples Collected in the Month of June, 2015 of Wet Season

Parameter	Source 1	Source 2	Source 3	Source 4	Source 5	Who Standard
Temperature	27.900±0.04	29.000±0.03	27.160±0.01	28.720±0.00	28.100±0.01	25-40
Ph	7.500±0.05	6.880±0.01	6.950±0.00	7.300±0.01	7.250±0.03	6.5-8.5
Colour	Muddy	Muddy	Muddy	Slightly Muddy	Muddy	Na
Odour	Un-Objectionable	Un-Objectionable	Un-Objectionable	Un-Objectionable	Un-Objectionable	Na
BOD	258.100±0.01	254.900±0.03	290.500±0.02	285.500±0.05	270.200±0.02	20-40
TSS	0.060±0.01	0.050±0.00	0.060±0.01	0.050±0.00	0.060±0.00	Na
TDS	86.850±0.03	70.000±0.01	78.500±0.02	73.200±0.01	80.000±0.01	500
TS	86.910±0.02	69.500±0.00	78.560±0.01	73.250±0.01	80.060±0.02	500
Conductivity	2.090±0.01	2.450±0.02	2.200±0.01	1.900±0.00	1.980±0.00	500

Note: BOD = Biochemical oxygen demand; TSS = Total suspended solid; TDS = Total dissolved solid; TS = Total solid, NA = Not available

The result of the physicochemical characteristics of the five samples collected in the month of July, 2015 of wet season were presented in Table 3. From the result, Sample 1, 3, 2 and 4 had the highest values of temperature, TSS, TDS, TS, pH, BOD and conductivity. Most samples were

muddy, unobjectionable and not determined in colour, odour and taste. Statistically, there were significant differences ($P < 0.05$) in the mean of the samples indicating that all the physicochemical parameters do not have the same influence on the samples.

Table 3. Physicochemical Characteristics of the Five Samples Collected in the mMonth of July, 2015 of Wet Season

Parameter	Source 1	Source 2	Source 3	Source 4	Source 5	Who Standard
Temperature	28.500±0.01	27.450±0.01	27.950±0.00	28.250±0.02	28.000±0.01	25-40
Ph	6.950±0.01	6.870±0.00	7.130±0.03	6.800±0.01	6.820±0.02	6.5-8.5
Colour	Muddy	Muddy	Muddy	Muddy	Muddy	Na
Odour	Un-Objectionable	Un-Objectionable	Un-Objectionable	Un-Objectionable	Un-Objectionable	Na
BOD	287.000±0.03	312.000±0.05	302.200±0.02	290.000±0.03	280.000±0.02	20-40
TSS	0.073±0.01	0.072±0.00	0.072±0.00	0.075±0.01	0.065±0.00	Na
TDS	80.000±0.02	78.500±0.01	70.000±0.01	82.500±0.02	70.000±0.01	500
TS	80.073±0.02	78.572±0.01	70.072±0.01	82.2575±0.02	70.065±0.01	500
Conductivity	2.260±0.01	2.200±0.01	2.000±0.00	2.600±0.02	2.300±0.01	500

Note: BOD = Biochemical oxygen demand; TSS = Total suspended solid; TDS = Total dissolved solid; TS = Total solid, NA = Not available

The results of the physicochemical parameters of the water samples collected in the months of May, June and July, 2015 of wet season were presented in Table 3. From the results, it

revealed that the pH value was slightly within neutral range (6.890 – 7.390). The temperature value ranged from 28.000 °C – 29.000 °C. The result of the present study revealed that the

colour was muddy and the odour was unobjectionable. The results of the TSS, TDS, TS and conductivity of the water samples were low and acceptable except BOD. Their taste was not determined. Statistically, there was significance

differences ($P < 0.05$) in the physicochemical parameters among the means of the three months indicating that physicochemical had influence on the variables of the wet season.

Table 4. Physicochemical Parameters of the Water Samples Collected in the Months of May, June and July, 2015 of Wet Season

Parameter	May	June	July	Who Standard
Temperature	29.330±0.01	28.200±0.01	28.007±0.02	25-40
Ph	7.390±0.00	7.200±0.00	6.890±0.01	6.5-8.5
Colour	Muddy	Muddy	Muddy	Na
Odour	Un-Objectionable	Un-Objectionable	Un-Objectionable	Na
BOD	259.200±0.01	275.100±0.00	291.200±0.01	20-40
TSS	0.050±0.01	0.060±0.01	0.070±0.02	Na
TDS	70.500±0.01	72.800±0.02	75.500±0.01	500
TS	73.200±0.04	75.800±0.02	79.100±0.02	500
Conductivity	1.740±0.01	2.010±0.02	2.280±0.01	500

Note: BOD = Biochemical oxygen demand; TSS = Total suspended solid; TDS = Total dissolved solid; TS = Total solid, NA = Not available

Physicochemical properties in dry season

The results of the physicochemical characteristics of the five samples collected in the month of December, 2015 of dry season were presented in Table 17. From the results, Sample 3, 5 and 4 had the highest values of temperature, pH, BOD, TSS, TDS, TS, and

conductivity. Most samples were muddy, unobjectionable and not determined in colour, odour and taste. Statistically, there were significant differences ($P < 0.05$) in the mean of the samples indicating that all the physicochemical parameters had diverse influence on the samples.

Table 5. Physicochemical Characteristics of the Five Samples Collected in the Month of December, 2015 of Dry Season

Parameter	Source 1	Source 2	Source 3	Source 4	Source 5	Who Standard
Temperature	27.400±0.01	28.600±0.01	31.500±0.02	30.000±0.01	29.500±0.01	25-40
Ph	6.600±0.01	6.480±0.01	6.700±0.00	6.400±0.01	6.300±0.01	6.5-8.5
Colour	Muddy	Muddy	Muddy	Muddy	Muddy	Na
Odour	Un-Objectionable	Un-Objectionable	Un-Objectionable	Un-Objectionable	Un-Objectionable	Na
BOD	75.000±0.01	90.000±0.02	85.000±0.03	67.000±0.01	91.000±0.02	20-40
TSS	1.300±0.01	1.200±0.01	1.550±0.01	1.650±0.02	1.460±0.01	Na
TDS	58.000±0.02	50.000±0.01	85.000±0.01	92.000±0.03	65.900±0.01	500
TS	59.300±0.01	51.200±0.01	86.550±0.03	93.650±0.02	67.360±0.01	500
Conductivity	1.900±0.01	2.000±0.01	2.130±0.02	2.300±0.01	2.150±0.00	500

Note: BOD = Biochemical oxygen demand; TSS = Total suspended solid; TDS = Total dissolved solid; TS = Total solid, NA = Not available

Table 6. Physicochemical Characteristics of the Five Samples Collected in the Month of January, 2016 of Dry Season

Parameter	Source 1	Source 2	Source 3	Source 4	Source 5	Who Standard
Temperature	28.600±0.01	27.500±0.00	29.000±0.01	28.000±0.01	28.500±0.01	25-40
Ph	6.900±0.01	6.000±0.00	6.450±0.01	6.300±0.00	6.450±0.02	6.5-8.5
Colour	Muddy	Muddy	Slightly Muddy	Muddy	Muddy	Na
Odour	Un-Objectionable	Un-Objectionable	Un-Objectionable	Un-Objectionable	Un-Objectionable	Na
BOD	80.000±0.03	78.000±0.02	73.000±0.01	72.000±0.01	76.000±0.02	20-40
TSS	1.500±0.00	1.300±0.00	1.200±0.01	1.000±0.00	1.000±0.02	Na
TDS	77.500±0.04	75.000±0.02	73.800±0.02	66.240±0.01	69.000±0.00	500
TS	79.000±0.08	76.300±0.01	75.000±0.01	67.240±0.01	70.000±0.00	500
Conductivity	1.900±0.01	1.850±0.00	2.000±0.01	1.980±0.00	1.960±0.01	500

Note: BOD = Biochemical oxygen demand; TSS = Total suspended solid; TDS = Total dissolved solid; TS = Total solid, NA = Not available

The results of the physicochemical characteristics of the five samples collected in the month of February, 2016 of dry season were presented in Table 6. From the results, Sample 3 and 1 had the highest values of temperature, conductivity, pH, BOD, TSS, TDS and TS. Most

samples were muddy, unobjectionable and not determined in colour, odour and taste. Statistically, there were significant differences ($P < 0.05$) in the mean of the samples indicating that all the physicochemical parameters don't have the same influence on the samples.

Table 7. Physicochemical Characteristics of the Five Samples Collected in the Month of February, 2016 of Dry Season

Parameter	Source 1	Source 2	Source 3	Source 4	Source 5	Who Standard
Temperature	27.800±0.01	28.200±0.01	28.000±0.00	28.400±0.00	28.320±0.00	25-40
Ph	6.080±0.01	6.130±0.01	6.400±0.02	6.100±0.00	6.300±0.02	6.5-8.5
Colour	Muddy	Muddy	Muddy	Muddy	Muddy	Na
Odour	Un-Objectionable	Un-Objectionable	Un-Objectionable	Un-Objectionable	Un-Objectionable	Na
BOD	68.500±0.02	70.000±0.03	72.500±0.02	74.000±0.02	73.000±0.02	20-40
TSS	1.000±0.02	1.300±0.01	1.100±0.00	1.120±0.01	1.600±0.03	Na
TDS	70.500±0.02	77.600±0.02	74.000±0.01	76.000±0.01	79.500±0.02	500
TS	71.500±0.02	78.900±0.02	75.100±0.01	77.120±0.01	81.100±0.02	500
Conductivity	2.000±0.00	1.850±0.00	1.940±0.01	1.920±0.02	1.880±0.02	500

Note: BOD = Biochemical oxygen demand; TSS = Total suspended solid; TDS = Total dissolved solid; TS = Total solid, NA = Not available

The results of the physicochemical parameters of the water samples collected in the months of December, January and February, 2015 - 2016 of dry season were presented in Table 20. From the results, it revealed that the pH value was slightly

within neutral range (6.200 – 6.500). The temperature value ranged from 28.800 °C – 29.000 °C. The result also revealed that the colour was muddy. The results of the TSS, TDS, TS and conductivity of the water samples were

low and acceptable except BOD. Their taste was not determined. Statistically, there was significance differences ($P < 0.05$) in the physicochemical parameters among the means of the three months indicating that physicochemical had influence on the variables of the wet season.

The results of the physicochemical characteristics of the five samples collected in the month of January, 2016 of dry season were presented in Table 7. From the results, Sample 3 and 1 had the highest values of temperature, conductivity, pH, BOD, TSS, TDS and TS. Most samples were muddy, unobjectionable and not determined in colour, odour and taste. Statistically, there were significant differences ($P < 0.05$) in the mean of the samples indicating that all the physicochemical parameters don't have the same influence on the samples.

The results of the physicochemical parameters of the water samples collected in the months of December, January and February, 2015 - 2016 of dry season were presented in Table 7. From the results, it revealed that the pH value was slightly within neutral range (6.200 – 6.500). The temperature value ranged from 28.800 °C – 29.000 °C. The result also revealed that the colour was muddy. The results of the TSS, TDS, TS and conductivity of the water samples were low and acceptable except BOD. Their taste was not determined. Statistically, there was significance differences ($P < 0.05$) in the physicochemical parameters among the means of the three months indicating that physicochemical had influence on the variables of the wet season.

Table 8. Physicochemical Parameters of the Water Samples Collected in the Month of December, January and February, 2015 -2016 of Dry Season

Parameter	December	January	February	Who Standard
Temperature	29.000±0.01	28.800±0.01	28.000±0.02	25-40
Ph	6.500±0.01	6.500±0.00	6.200±0.01	6.5-8.5
Colour	Muddy	Muddy	Muddy	Na
Odour	Un-Objectionable	Un-Objectionable	Un-Objectionable	Na
BOD	80.000±0.01	75.000±0.04	72.000±0.02	20-40
TSS	1.420±0.02	1.300±0.03	1.200±0.02	Na
TDS	70.500±0.01	27.800±0.02	75.500±0.03	500
TS	73.200±0.01	75.800±0.03	79.100±0.04	500
Conductivity	2.200±0.01	1.950±0.00	1.900±0.00	500

Note: BOD = Biochemical oxygen demand; TSS = Total suspended solid; TDS =Total dissolved solid; TS = Total solid, NA = Not available

The results in Table 1 - 3 are varying physicochemical influences on all the sources of the sampling sites. From the result, it revealed that the pH value was slightly within neutral range (6.200 – 6.500). The temperature value ranged from 28.800 °C – 29.000 °C. The temperature range was higher during the wet than dry season (Tables 22 and 26). The temperature values for both seasons were within the World Health Organization (WHO) Standard of 25 - 40 °C and also fall within the normal temperature range supportive of good

surface water quality which is 0 °C to 30 °C (Olatunji *et al.*, 2011). The temperature of any water body affects the rate of proliferation of microorganisms and controls the rate of all chemical reactions (Samuel *et al.* 2017). The result of the present study also revealed that the colour was muddy. The physical or visual observable dirtiness of the water was an evidence of water pollution. The dirtiness could be attributed to direct emptying of waste materials into the water, a phenomenon that is common in Nigeria and Africa at large and also

to precipitation which re-suspends sediments. Akubuenyi *et al.*, (2013) reported similar findings where he stated that the muddiness of a water resource could be attributed to direct emptying of material into the water source and are indicators of water pollution. The results of the TSS, TDS, TS and conductivity of the water samples were low and acceptable except BOD and colour. The results revealed that the total suspended solids (TSS), total dissolved solids (TDS) and total solids (TS) of all the water samples are in agreement with the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) standard. Total dissolved solids (TDS) in drinking water has been associated with natural sources, sewage urban run-off, industrial waste water and chemical used in the water treatment process (EPA, 2002). Also, the water samples were observed to have unobjectionable odour. Many researchers observed similar findings ((Samuel *et al.* 2017; Akubuenyi *et al.*, 2013; Agboli *et al.* (2017)). Their taste was not determined. The high BOD and COD values may be due to the discharge of untreated or incompletely treated industrial effluents into the stream. The BOD values are high probably due to discharge of domestic wastes especially defecation activities and poorly executed agricultural activities near the stream banks (Esharegoma *et al.*, 2018). In the present study, the conductivity value which is the measure of the ability of water to conduct an electric current was significantly low for each of the samples and indicated a low salt concentration in the water. Akubuenyi *et al.* (2013) said that the low conductivity values of water samples imply that the dissolved salts are minimal. Similar findings were also reported by Akoro and Adiyah, (2007), Alam *et al.* (2007) and Ababiaka and Sule, (2011). Statistically, there was significance differences ($P < 0.05$) in the physicochemical parameters among the means of the three months indicating that physicochemical properties had influence on the variables of the wet season. Comparatively, wet season had more physicochemical attributes than dry season in Obibia Stream though not significant ($P > 0.05$) using two tailed paired T-TEST as presented in Appendix XVIII. This implies that both seasons

had almost these effects on the physicochemical parameters of Obibia Stream.

Correlationally, there was non – significant but very strong positive correlation ($r = 0.992$, $P > 0.05$) between some selected physicochemical properties and bacteriological content of the water samples in the wet season while there was non – significant but moderate negative correlation ($r = -0.501$, $P > 0.05$) between some selected physicochemical properties and bacteriological content of the water samples in the dry season as presented and shown in Appendices XIXa, XIXb, XXa, XXb and Figures 5 and 6, respectively. Thus, from the correlation results, bacteria content of the Obibia Stream water can be reduced greatly by decreasing activities that lead to high physicochemical contents both in the wet and dry seasons. Tamungang *et al.* (2016) reported that the sulphate content of the water samples were highly significantly and negatively correlated ($r = -1.000$, $p < 0.01$) with the bacteria (enterobacteria, *E. coli* and *Streptococcus*) content of the samples, whereas magnesium content was found to be significantly and positively correlated ($r = 1.000$, $p < 0.05$) with the bacteria content of the samples. Looking at the sulphate levels of all samples (ranging from 0.043 to 0.17 mg/l) comparable to the WHO and EPA value of 250 mg/l, it means the water is prone to bacterial contamination. Thus, from the correlation results, the bacteria content of the water can be reduced greatly by increasing its sulphate content and decreasing its magnesium content.

Conclusion

Obibia stream has been a source of portable water for drinking purposes, domestic purposes and urban agriculture. These activities, as important as they are, create and release contaminants into the stream. The physicochemical indices including those of public health significance were high as established in this study as a veritable case of negative human impact in the environment and negative effect of precipitation. Significant variation in physicochemical parameters were

observed between rainy and dry seasons. Correlationally, there was non-significant but very strong positive correlation between some selected physicochemical properties and bacteriological content of the water samples in the wet season while there was non – significant but moderate negative between some selected physicochemical properties and bacteriological content of the water samples in the dry season. This highlights the urgent need for the proper treatment of the surface water of Obibia Stream with appropriate method (s) before consumption or any other domestic usage.

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